

METHODS OF TEACHING MATHEMATICS ON THE BASIS OF THE PRINCIPLES OF HUMANISM

Feruza Sharopova

Teacher in mathematics

Secondary school No. 15 in Termez city

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645784>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

mathematics, humanitarian education, method, humanitarian principle, test, evaluation of assignments

ABSTRACT

the article analyzes the role of mathematics in the implementation of the liberal educational model. It is based on the need for methods of studying mathematics and assessing its results based on the principles of humanism.

All over the world and always mathematics was taken seriously and with respect. Today, its importance has increased significantly. Life shows that in countries with a high level of economic development, the level of mathematical education is almost at all levels of society. Many professions that serve modern society require good knowledge of mathematics. A low level of mathematical education leads not only to the restriction of freedom in the choice of profession. A person entering any market - a clothing or securities market - must have a certain level of mathematical education and a mathematical culture. At this time, without knowledge of mathematics, any successful entrepreneurial activity is impossible in the conditions of commercialization of the life of the whole society as a whole. And not only entrepreneurial projects, but also all modern technologies require good mathematical knowledge from employees. Mathematical literacy is one of the most

important indicators that determines the effectiveness of the economic, technological, cultural and other development of society today. According to media materials, for example, higher mathematics knowledge and Information Technology in Japan is one of the necessary conditions for employment, even for working specialties. More than twenty years ago, the government of the United States set the goal of turning American Mathematics Education into the best education in the world, and they have been quite successful towards this goal of "feeding" the saltiest minds of mathematics science around the world. Unfortunately, the results of surveys and examinations conducted in schools of Uzbekistan in recent times show that the level of mathematics literacy of our schoolchildren is very low (we do not take into account the results of International Mathematics Olympiads and competitions). In our opinion, this is due to the fact that in

elementary school, students receive distorted ideas about mathematics itself, its concepts. The main mathematical skills, for example, the arithmetic skills that are so necessary in the life of a person, are not taught in a school hidden behind the loud sign "Development Education". Improperly constructed methods, improperly selected exercises overload some parts of the brain, lead young students to mental disorders. Disadvantages of primary mathematics education then affect Secondary School, in this case, correction classes are created for the purpose of correcting the situation, mathematics programs are simplified, hours allocated to mathematics are reduced. The reason why mathematics destroys the wonderful traditions of education is also the wide application of the test method, which puts slow but deep-thinking students at an extreme disadvantage in assessing the knowledge of the students. It is known that the process of finding different ways to solve a problem in the test is replaced by the process of finding the answer from the proposed ones, that is, from the ready ones. The current assessment system focuses more on developing the memory of the students rather than developing the thinking of the teachers. It is known that the process of finding different ways to solve a problem in the test is replaced by the process of finding the answer from the proposed ones, that is, from the ready ones. The current assessment system focuses more on developing the memory of the students rather than developing the thinking of the teachers. Now, the system of control over the knowledge introduced in the school determines what the student does not know, rather than what the student knows, and the assessment is determined by

subtracting their shortcomings rather than summarizing the success of the schoolchildren. Evaluation criteria do not determine the level of understanding and awareness of learning by the students. Control and test assignments, including school examinations, do not evoke the active conscious mind of the student. At the same time, the internal integration of mathematics is disrupted, which is designed not only as a set of practical recipes in schoolchildren, but also to form an idea as a system of logical coherent knowledge, deductive science. Standardized tests examine students' ability to remember and apply learned syllables in a planned manner. Even tasks designed to assess a high level of mathematical skills often require the ability to remember the appropriate formula and correctly perform substitutions in order to get the right answer. However, the actual teaching of mathematics involves the construction of their interpretations and their corresponding to the available knowledge. Teachers of mathematics (as well as external examiners) should assess not only the ability to "swallow" and "give", but also the level and complexity of understanding. In our opinion, providing teachers with information on the latest technologies of assessment and thus supporting assessment in the school should be regarded as a basic element of teaching, and not an addition to it. It is necessary to systematically teach these technologies to the students of the pedagogical specialty of the university, and teachers in the process of improving their skills. If we turn to the practice of teaching in the United States, then there is a tendency to reduce the number of standardized tests based on

multiple choices and replace it with a form of assessment of the performance of tasks. According to this form, in order to assess the performance of the task, the assignments themselves should be real examples of the development of skills, and not artificial constructions. The main emphasis here is on achieving the right answer, not by giving up the wrong answers, as in many competitions, but by clever operations. When one method of evaluation is better advertised than others, it seems that it is necessary to stop the trend of simply seeing the situation. A system that supports different assessment methods and ensures proper use of each of them should become in demand. Let the test, built on multiple choices, take its rightful place in this system and have the same rights as other methods. We also need to study the impact of assessment on learning more deeply (although much has been written about it) because there is no such thing as assessment except learning; they are in dynamic interaction. For several decades, mathematics has been under unprecedented pressure from the public on both its content and methods of teaching, and on the evaluation of their results. Therefore, both in secondary schools and in higher institutions, the teaching of mathematics and the content of mathematical education are constantly revised either in the direction of more visualization and visual modeling, or in the direction of revealing its social position. In fact, the intensity of the movement of our time requires a clear orientation from the teachers of mathematics in all the main areas of scientific development of the subject they teach. The new tasks of the secondary school require from him to improve not only teaching and education,

but also to a certain extent scientific activity, and this cannot be imagined without an in-depth study of the subject as a theory of its subject and the process of its study. The only system of scientific explanation. Great importance was attached to the pedagogical principle-the principle of humanization of Education, which was proclaimed in the 90 - ies of the last century in our country in the elimination of negative trends in the spiritual sphere of society. The basis of this principle is the establishment of a new goal, which sets the human personality as a priority task, the development of its creative potential, the formation of a humane worldview, which is a blessing both for society and for the individual himself. However, in those years, under the slogan of humanization and humanization in the secondary school, an "attack" on specific subjects began, the hours allocated to mathematics began to be reduced, the curricula were reduced. In addition, this process has led to the emergence of classes in the humanities and even whole schools, which were given and still receives extreme importance to the humanities, causing harm to the natural and Mathematical Sciences. We recognize that individuals are oriented in different types - humanitarian and natural sciences, and in this connection, the need to take into account them in the process of educational activities of students, especially in the organization of forms of pedagogical assistance in the choice of profession. At the same time, we believe that the subjects (especially children, since they have not yet fully grown up for this) in the secondary school should not be mechanically divided into humanitarian and non-humanitarian Sciences, since all sciences are included.

The natural-mathematical cycle is the only part of the universal culture and, with proper preparation, one can perform all without exception humanitarian functions. Like all other sciences, mathematics requires a respectful attitude, because it contributes fundamental to the creative development of the individual, logical and analytical thinking, spatial imagination. The use of these opportunities as a subject of learning with a specific humanitarian potential and using the methods of humanization of the educational process has a great impact on the development of students' creative abilities, logical and linguistic culture, raising morale. Recently, the role of mathematics in modern society as a means of socialization and humanization of an individual has been strengthened. Mathematics is increasingly regarded as a subject of study as a general cultural science. In fact, such characteristics and qualities as the effectiveness of thinking and perception of a person, the development of his mental abilities and objectionable speech, the logical usefulness of evidence, can be a real result of mathematical education, if it is organized on the basis of prints. The development of the creative abilities of students in the process of teaching mathematics in many ways depends on what tools and methods are used in teaching, but the latter, of course, should correspond to the humanitarian approach. The creation of conditions that will ensure the student's success in school, a sense of pleasure from educational work, is a necessary condition for the humanization of mathematics education. Speaking about the humanization of mathematical education, we propose to organize the educational process in such a way that

mathematical concepts, knowledge and skills have a personal meaning for the student. In this, the student ceases to be the "target" of achieving the result, but also becomes the main goal of the educational process. It is wrong to think that humanization of education is only the competence of humanitarian Sciences. Mathematics provides the process of humanization with a huge field of activity. This is a classic of Mathematical Science A. Puankaren's view points out that "the main goal of teaching mathematics is to develop certain abilities of the mind." Analysis of various historical facts and data on the subject of mathematics, discussion of worldview issues, individual approach to students in solving mathematical problems of different complexity, creation of an environment of humanism in students can be attributed to the methods of humanization of mathematics teaching. Cooperation in the student community is designed to arouse interest in creative activity, which is expressed in the desire to know in depth what the child's aspiring mind hears. Here it is necessary to emphasize the idea that the humanization of the methods of studying mathematical sciences should be carried out not on the basis of simplification and loss of their truly profound mathematical meaning, but, as we have proposed, by resorting to historical materials. Humanization is not an increase in the number of subjects in the socio-humanitarian profile in the educational program, but the use of internal humanitarian resources and guidelines of the subject under study. Accordingly, the process of humanization of mathematical education is much more than the involvement of students in the culture of humanism, and it is not possible

to reduce it only by increasing the time it takes to study it. It is talking about another "ideology" of teaching, the "ideology" of the use of internal spiritual and aesthetic potential, the history and content of mathematics itself, its methodological concepts, as well as the methods of humanizing teaching, the use of organizational forms and tools. Humanization of mathematical methods of education involves the establishment and achievement of the generally accepted objectives of the educational process in the classroom - teaching, developing and educating. At the same time, the implementation of the principle of humanism in the teaching of mathematics can go in such directions as the formation of the worldview of humanism in students, the development of general scientific skills, speech and thinking, and the deepening of both theoretical and practical direction. If the teaching of mathematics in a simple secondary school is built on the construction of "mastering= understanding + application", then in the conditions of a humanistic approach to the educational process, it must be built on the construction of "mastering= mastering + application". Putting the personality of the student in the center of the educational process, humanization, which requires him to translate into the highest value and content of school activities, implies, first of all, the change in the application of the system of teaching methods. It is necessary to use methods that humanize the process of teaching mathematics, they are aimed not only at the average able-bodied student, but also at the professional

personality of the student. The consideration of students' inclinations, abilities and interests is based on the focus from "mathematical development" to "development through mathematics". Famous mathematician V.A. Dalinger emphasizes very correctly, "in the educational process, it is necessary to pay attention to education with the help of mathematics, first of all, mathematics should be taught to all students, and not only to the elite." Humanization of mathematical education from the point of view of innovative processes involves the transition from the multiplication of the volume of all types of data to the teaching of cognitive activity of students: the acquisition of a new part of knowledge in mathematics through problem research and its use in practice. Innovations that affect the issues of humanization of mathematical methods of education also imply the completion of the course of mathematics with emotional materials. To do this, it is necessary to familiarize students not only with the history of the emergence and development of individual concepts (sections) of mathematics, but also with the struggle of ideas, their future destiny, etc. The implementation of methods of humanization in education will be possible only in the presence of sufficiently qualified teachers. In our opinion, in the preparation of the school teacher, including the teacher of mathematics, the outstanding scientists in the field of basic specialization, no less prominent scientists in pedagogy, psychology and socio-humanitarian sciences should be engaged.

References:

1. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/informatizatsiya-obrazovaniya-kak-faktor-integratsii-nachalnogo-obucheniya-matematike-i-informatike>
2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/razvitie-gumanitarnoy-kultury-studentov-v-protsesse-prepodavaniya-matematiki>
3. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osobennosti-pedagogicheskoy-kultury-uchitelya-matematiki-i-puti-ee-formirovaniya>
4. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/monitoring-sformirovannosti-professionalnoy-kompetentnosti-bakalavra-pedagogicheskogo-obrazovaniya-po-profilyu-matematika-v-oblasti>